

A Service-Based Management Architecture for Intelligent Cross-Domain Orchestration in 6G Networks

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Abstract—This paper focuses on the design of a Service-Based Management Architecture (SBMA) that enables intelligent, cross-domain, and sustainable orchestration. SBMA adopts a service-based paradigm to abstract domain heterogeneity, integrates distributed AI-driven control, and provides a foundation for achieving unified management. The proposed architecture is illustrated by mapping specific domains (such as the radio access (RAN), transport, and core networks) to the architecture, demonstrating how domain-specific orchestration aligns with SBMA principles and interfaces. A representative experiment validates the architecture’s capabilities, and the results show rapid recovery times for redeploying RAN, core, and transport components, highlighting the resilience and agility of the proposed approach.

Index Terms—end-to-end services, unified network architecture, service-based architecture, orchestration

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution toward sixth generation (6G) networks introduces unprecedented requirements for scalability, openness, and sustainability across heterogeneous domains, including the Radio Access Network (RAN), Core Network (CN), and transport network. Emerging use cases such as extended reality, disaster response, digital twins, and industrial automation demand not only ultra-reliable, low-latency communication but also intelligent and sustainable service delivery across distributed infrastructures. Current 5G management frameworks, such as [1], [2], though advanced, are limited in their ability to provide holistic, cross-domain orchestration, particularly regarding end-to-end (E2E) service continuity, dynamic adaptability, and environmental considerations. Addressing this aspect, the paper in [3] recently presented a unified architecture for 6G networks that integrates Open RAN, distributed intelligence, and AI-native orchestration to improve scalability, openness,

and sustainability. The work outlines the key components of the architecture, deployment scenarios, and research directions to ensure energy efficiency, interoperability, and trustworthiness in future networks. However, the complete E2E service management framework is not yet fully defined. An interesting approach was proposed by [4], in which the authors considered an intent-based network management architecture; however, their focus was mainly on reliable intent interpretation using large language models, and the E2E framework architecture was not discussed.

The main motivation for this work is to address the fragmentation of current management and orchestration systems and to enable cross-domain intelligence for 6G networks. Existing frameworks (e.g., [1], [2], [5]) operate in isolation, focus on specific domains (such as RAN or CN), and often use static interfaces and hierarchical control models that limit scalability and flexibility. This fragmented approach limits seamless end-to-end orchestration and prevents dynamic service continuity when resources must be relocated or reconfigured across domains. Additionally, current frameworks lack standardized mechanisms for integrating AI-driven closed loops that coordinate learning and decision-making across different domains. As a result, the potential of distributed intelligence is underutilized, with most optimizations restricted to local or domain-specific scopes. Meanwhile, sustainability is becoming a fundamental design criterion for future networks, yet existing orchestration mechanisms still provide limited support for energy-aware decisions or environmentally optimized service management. These gaps motivate the design of an Service-Based Management Architecture (SBMA) that enables intelligent, cross-domain, and sustainable orchestration. SBMA adopts a service-based paradigm to abstract domain heterogeneity, integrates distributed AI-driven control, and provides a foundation for realizing the unified management vision outlined in [3].

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II. TOWARDS UNIFIED ARCHITECTURE

This section provides an overview of current architectural trends towards 6G, focusing on open, distributed paradigms enabling end-to-end intelligence and orchestration, and grouped by the corresponding Standards Development Organization (SDO).

A. ETSI

In the quest of an unified architecture, ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG) Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) defines the Management and Orchestration (MANO) framework [1]. The latter, composed by the Network Functions Virtualisation Orchestrator (NFVO), the VNF Manager (VNFM) and the Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM), allows the lifecycle management, resource orchestration, and chaining of Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) into Network Services (NSs) decoupled from the underlying Network Functions Virtualisation Infrastructure (NFVI) hardware. Over the years, ETSI NFV has been further evolving MANO by incorporating new paradigms such as automation and intent-based management.

In parallel, ETSI Experiential Network Intelligence (ENI), leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) to enhance network automation, particularly in the management and orchestration of network slices, by leveraging the Observe-Orient-Decide-Act (OODA) control loop to enable dynamic self-adaptation for improved performance and user experience [5]. Moreover, ENI incorporates a policy management block for context-aware, metadata-driven policies, enhancing network slicing security [6].

B. O-RAN Alliance

The O-RAN Alliance defines an open, cloud-native RAN architecture with disaggregated components. i.e., Open-Central Unit (O-CU), Open-Distributed Unit (O-DU), Open-Radio Unit (O-RU), and interoperable interfaces. At its core, it embeds intelligence in the form of RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs): the Near-RT RIC hosts xApps for control within 10 ms–1 s, while the Non-RT RIC, hosted in the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO), runs rApps for policy and optimization over seconds. Overarching this architecture, the SMO provides orchestration and management capabilities, connecting to the O-Cloud, and hosting O-RAN functions on a hybrid cloud platform with pooled compute, storage, and virtualization resources.

In O-RAN, ML lifecycle operations are supported through the AI Training Host Platform (ATHP) and the AI Inference Host Platform (AIHP), which separate training and inference operations to optimize compute placement across cloud-edge hierarchies. Nevertheless, despite generally promoting AI-ML r/xApps, the O-RAN architecture lacks a unified AI execution substrate across the RAN, so end-to-end AI orchestration proposals often rely on RICs.

C. ITU

Multiple ITU groups are responsible for standardization of non-radio aspects of IMT-2030 technologies. Notably, ITU-T Study Group 13 (SG13) is promoting the native embedding of autonomy and AI via definition of the Autonomous Networks (AN) framework (Rec. Y.3061), and the Native AI architecture (Rec. Y.3172 and FG-AINN). Additionally, ITU-T Study Group 2 (SG2) defines the AITOM framework (Rec. M.3080), which describes the operational business logic for AI-driven OAM, and the M.fmcdns work item, which serves as the primary point of harmonisation between ITU-T SG2 and 3GPP SA5 for “Cross-Domain Orchestration”. Furthermore, it is working on a natively autonomous and intelligent architecture codified in M.fmcdns (AN/AITOM) that will use SBMA-like principles for inter-domain federation and service-based interoperability. Finally, the ITU-T Focus Group on Machine Learning for Future Networks (FG-ML5G) defines a network-agnostic AI/ML pipeline that enables overlay ML workflows across RAN, Core, and management domain.

D. TM Forum

The TM Forum developed the Open Digital Architecture (ODA), shifting from traditional operational support systems to a cloud-native, modular, and interoperable framework that supports Business-to-Business-to-X (B2B2X) service models. It emphasizes security, scalability, and flexibility, enabling agile service delivery and integration of AI for network automation. Overall, ODA represents an unifying architectural approach that can integrate with other standardization initiatives such as ETSI’s and O-RAN’s, creating a cohesive ecosystem for future-proof, automated, and interoperable next-generation services.

III. PROPOSED UNIFIED NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

A. The Need for Unification

The 6G vision adopts the “network of networks” concept, integrating multiple domains into a highly sustainable and scalable AI-native architecture designed to address diverse network requirements [7]. However, managing these domains (e.g., (O-)RAN, CN, and transport for interconnected Terrestrial Network (TN) and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN)) must be highly distributed and interoperable, as the requested network services are highly dynamic, accommodating the QoS needs of different tenants and allocating varying network resources. To this end, integration of Non-Public Networks (NPNs), satellite components, CN functions, and transport links to support complex 6G use cases (e.g., emergency communications, enhanced mobile broadband scenarios) should be conducted in a coordinated and efficient manner. In this context, abstraction mechanisms are required for managing these heterogeneous domains, along with the definition of common interfaces to enable communication and data exchange between them. To address these challenges, a unified reference architecture for a 6G system is presented here, aiming to facilitate management processes of the operators and enable end-to-end service delivery.

B. Proposed Overall Architecture

Based on the trends identified by the work of the different SDOs, Figure 1 presents a modular architecture, inspired in [8], for unified cross-domain service orchestration and intelligent management in multi-domain environments, leveraging a SBMA approach to create the central coordination layer. The SBMA enables orchestrated service control and interaction across heterogeneous domains (denoted as Domain A to Domain N, like RAN, Core, Transport), each comprising a Domain Management Orchestrator (DMO). Each domain is also equipped with local AI Agent entities, and one or multiple Infrastructure Domain Managers (IDMs). The DMO interacts with its underlying IDMs to manage Points of Presence (PoPs) for the Life-Cycle Management (LCM) of a set of virtualised Network Functions (NFs) grouped as NSs implementing the different mobile network entities (e.g., O-CU, O-DU, gNB, mobile CN functions (i.e., AMF, SMF, UPF), near-RT RICs), like the ETSI NFV MANO framework, or the LCM of traffic flows configured in the transport network interconnecting PoPs hosting virtualised NFs through a Software Defined Networking (SDN) controller, thus enabling autonomous domain-level control and adaptation to realise an end-to-end view. AI agents are realized in the form of connected tuples, namely Monitoring System (MS), Analytics Engine (AE), Decision Engine (DE) and ACT, inspired by the ETSI ENI OODA control loop, which exchange monitoring data and models through the data continuum substrate with the AI/ML subsystem domain. Inter-domain interoperability is achieved through the Service Adapter (SA) entity that interfaces each domain with the SBMA. Service adapters collect requests from the SBMA bus, interpret and translate them into requests to the right DMO.

At the core of the orchestration logic lies the Inter-Domain Management Orchestrator (IDMO), which performs E2E service orchestration and coordination, supported by intelligent conflict resolution mechanisms and AI-driven decision engines. The IDMO also acts as a Management Service Consumer of the services produced by the Management Service Producers (i.e., the different underlying domains) and interacts with centralized registries, including the Management Domain Registry, Network Service (NS) catalogue, and Resource Registry. The messages exchanged between the different domains and the IDMO enable dynamic discovery, configuration, and resource availability across domains. The architecture includes exposure capabilities to external Operations Support Systems/Business Support Systems (OSS/BSS) via standardized APIs (e.g., CAMARA APIs), allowing integration with external platforms and vertical applications. The system is underpinned by a Data Continuum that spans all domains, enabling continuous data exchange, real-time analytics, and feedback loops to support AI-enabled optimization, intent-based policy enforcement, and autonomous network adaptation.

C. Service Bus

Following the SBA architecture proposed by 3GPP for the mobile CN, the logical connection between different domains

and end-to-end orchestration is achieved through the cross-domain service-based management bus. Through this bus, the domains register with IDMO and exchange information objects (e.g., JSON-formatted messages) to populate IDMO database modules by announcing service catalogs, resource availability, geographical footprint, and transport network interconnection points to enable service discovery functionality and lifecycle management operations. Depending on the scenario and expected features (i.e., scale, target domain, latency, etc.) and focus (messaging, cache and memory, event streaming), various solutions can be considered, including Apache Kafka, gRPC, Apache Pulsar, RabbitMQ, 0MQ, Redis, MQTT, or cloud-native tools. However, the choice of communication protocol and messaging can be left to implementation.

D. Inter-Domain Management Orchestrator

The IDMO, whose internal proposed architecture is shown in Figure 2, serves as the central intelligence of the SBMA-based orchestration framework, enabling unified end-to-end orchestration and coordination across the heterogeneous DMOs. It is organized into three primary elements: the Intent Manager, the Lifecycle Manager, and the Service Adapter. The Intent Manager serves as the entry point of the orchestration framework and is responsible for receiving, interpreting, validating, and decomposing user intents. It ensures that service requests, whether expressed in structured or natural language, are converted into machine-actionable objectives. The Intent Manager comprises three main submodules. The North Bound Interface (NBI) receives well-formatted intents from external systems or user interfaces. This component can be enhanced with the Intent Declarator submodule, which assists users through natural language interaction powered by Large Language Models (LLMs). The Intent Validator ensures the feasibility of the request by interacting with the corresponding database (DB) modules to verify the availability of required descriptors, computing resources, deployment zones, and compatible technologies. This process prevents the orchestration system from attempting deployments that the current infrastructure or configuration cannot support. The Intent Decomposer and Provider Selector break down high-level intents into domain-specific sub-intents. For example, a request for a “5G connectivity service” may be decomposed into separate RAN, CN, and transport intents. The decomposer also performs logical dependency checks; for instance, if a user requests only a RAN service, the module verifies the existence of a compatible 5G CN instance. Finally, it selects the appropriate domains to fulfill each sub-intent based on resource availability and requirements.

After the intent is decomposed and the appropriate domains are selected, the Lifecycle Manager module coordinates the orchestration sequence and manages the operational state of each sub-service throughout its lifecycle, including instantiation, configuration, scaling, and termination. It determines the correct order of execution, ensuring dependencies between decomposed intents, and produces corresponding messages to the underlying orchestration layers through the SBMA

Fig. 1: Proposed unified architecture combining several domains via SBMA.

Fig. 2: IDMO architecture and corresponding components.

bus. Requests are dispatched to the SA module, serving as the communication interface between the orchestration logic and the underlying DMOs at each domain. SA subscribes to and publishes messages on the cross-domain SBMA message bus, mediating the exchange of operational data between the Lifecycle Manager, external systems, and the DB module.

IV. DOMAIN LEVEL COMPONENTS AND DESCRIPTIONS

In this section, we analyze selected single network domains from the perspective of the unified architecture and map their functional elements to the proposed solution.

A. O-RAN

O-RAN, thoroughly studied and standardized by the Open RAN Alliance, is based on the disaggregation and modularity of the radio component. Recently, this concept has also been considered in other network domains, such as NTN or NPN. As mentioned in Sec. II, two key O-RAN controllers, the Near-Real-Time RIC and the Non-Real-Time RIC, are responsible for controlling network operations. The latter is part of the SMO module, whose role essentially overlaps with that of the DMO (see Fig. 1). It should be noted that the Near-RT RIC, although not located in the DMO, controls the functioning of the underlying xApp and thus logically belongs to the DMO. O-Cloud is widely considered in O-RAN; consequently, the applied VIM directly maps to the IDM module in the unified architecture. Two key types of services can be identified: all NFs related to deployed units (O-RU, O-CU, O-DU, Near-RT RIC) and all installed applications (mainly rApps, xApps, and eventually dApps). The mapping between the domains and the proposed architecture is included in Tab. I.

B. 5G-Core

In the context of 5G CN, the SBA has already been adopted in the official standard releases. The approach proposed there directly specifies a set of dedicated network functions, such as User Plane Function (UPF), Session Management Function (SMF), and Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), among others. From an implementation perspective,

Domain name	DMO	NF	IDM	Notes
O-RAN	SMO	Applications are rApps, xApps, dApps and NFs are O-RU, O-DU, O-CU, etc.	O-Cloud Virtualized Infrastructure Manager	Although Near RT RIC does not belong to SMO, it manages the deployment of xApps, thus logically is managed by DMO
5G Core	Realised with ETSI MANO (NFV and VNF) included in stacks like ONAP or Open Source MANO (OSM)	Various functions specified in the 3GPP standards, such as AMF, SMF, UPF, etc.	ETSI MANO: VIM	5G standards for 5G CN deployment can align with ETSI MANO guidelines towards network virtualization and software-defined networking
NTN	No open SMO tailored to NTN; however, vendors provide SMO for satellite purposes	As in 5G Core, if NTN realizes similar functionalities	Not specified	Several standards define aspects related to network slice management (TS 28.531, TS 28.533); the latter specifies a service-based management architecture that enables role-based interactions
Transport	Network Slice Controller (NSC)	Flow configuration	SDN controller (e.g., Teraflow SDN Controller)	There are no NFs, but we consider the configuration of flows on the forwarding components. The transport network slicing framework is defined in IETF RFC 9543.
NPN	Vendor-specific WLAN controllers; also TSN CNC, TSN CUC	WiFi Access Point, UPF, I-UPF	Not specified	In the context of NPN, various aspects are yet to be defined in the context of automation and virtualization
AI/ML	AI Orchestrator (e.g. Air-Flow)	Typical to AI domain, such as Inference functions, Model training etc.	Data Manager (e.g. Helm/KServe)	Here, we do not consider the cloud-specific solutions applied by hyperscalers for offering their services

TABLE I: Mapping of the domain elements into the unified architecture.

5G networks can follow the ETSI MANO guidelines and implement the NFVO and VNF, which correspond to the DMO in the unified architecture. The IDM can be directly associated with the VIM from ETSI MANO. In practice, open solutions such as ONAP or OSM, as well as vendor-specific tools, realize this concept for 5G networks.

C. Non-Terrestrial Networks

The integration of 3GPP-enabled NTN systems calls for advanced network orchestration paradigms adapting to the spatio-temporal dynamics of satellite systems [9] and such to allow inter-working with 3GPP terrestrial counterpart [10]. To achieve these goals, there exists no specific NTN open architecture, whereby the foundation for NTN orchestration set in [11] along with the specific ETSI MANO and ENI architectural building blocks, illustrated earlier in this paper, are taken as reference by satellite vendors for implementing the needed SMO functionalities.

D. Transport domain

The transport domain manages all infrastructure (including wired and wireless) that provides intra- and inter-domain connectivity, including RAN, CN, NTN, and NPN. Management of this domain is divided into two main roles: DMO and IDM. The Network Slice Controller (NSC) serves as the DMO in the transport domain, managing connectivity through network slices and orchestrating their requests, realization, and lifecycle control. It consists of four components: a NBI that adapts transport-related requests into the appropriate format (i.e., IETF Network Slice Service (RFC 9543)); the Mapper, which provides the necessary context to each request to ensure successful realization; the Realizer, which selects the most suitable technology to implement the slice (such as L2VPN or

L3VPN) and translates the request into SDN controller configurations; and a database that stores information about deployed slices. In this context, the NSC serves as the DE. The IDM function is provided by the SDN controller, which manages the transport infrastructure (e.g., TeraflowSDN controller).

E. Non-3GPP RAN domain and NPN

The non-3GPP domain consists of multi-radio access technology (RAT) deployment, where, in addition to cellular RAT, IEEE 802.11 RAT is also used to serve users in different verticals for non-public network deployments. Additionally, to support end-to-end time-sensitive applications, wired time-sensitive networking (TSN) switches are included in the infrastructure (see Fig. 3). At its core, the non-3GPP domain consists of the DMO, which interfaces northbound with the IDMO while orchestrating the operation of the IEEE 802.11 Access Point (AP) controller, as well as the Central Network Controller (CNC) and Central User Controller (CUC) for the TSN part. All controllers and the DMO are interconnected via the Domain Data Fabric (DDF), while DB storage is provided for telemetry data and application requirements. A domain digital twin (DDT) entity is expected to perform automatic scheduling based on application requirements from the CUC, real-time telemetry data from the CNC telemetry DB and real-time topology monitoring DB. The non-3GPP DMO will interact with the SMO of the O-RAN DMO via cross-domain SBMA. In the southbound direction, IDM interacts with cellular base stations and IEEE 802.11 APs using a unified approach that follows O-RAN principles. Architecture functional specifications are assigned as follows: DDT is responsible for decision and analytic engine functions; CNC and the AP controller are responsible for analytics, action, and monitoring engine functions; and network nodes are responsible for action engine functions.

Fig. 3: Non-3GPP RAN Domain.

F. AI/ML Subsystem

As shown in Fig. 2, the AI/ML domain may also interact with other domains via the SBMA bus to offer its services. Thus, the AI/ML subsystem provides intelligent services to multiple domains, aligning with the concept of AI-native architecture. The internal components include an AI/ML Orchestrator, which coordinates the lifecycle management of intelligent services; a Data Management module, responsible for all data operations (utilizing the Data Continuum bus depicted in Fig. 1) and the chaining of tuple components; a Training module, which performs the ML training process; a Sandbox building block, used for offline training and testing of ML models; and a Model Registry component, where pre-trained models are stored. Through the AI/ML Orchestrator, the subsystem receives requests from different domains to develop AI/ML pipelines as connected tuples (MS, AE, DE, ACT) for three main purposes: (i) *training pipeline*, which links the functional tuple building blocks to perform all required operations for training an ML model. This pipeline is also extended to incorporate distributed learning mechanisms, such as federated learning and multi-agent reinforcement learning; (ii) *inference pipeline*, which serves an already trained model to an inference host for online operation; (iii) *evaluation pipeline*, which monitors the online inference and assesses the model performance.

V. EMERGENCY COMMUNICATION FOR DISASTER RESILIENCE

To verify the performance of the proposed unified architecture, a dedicated experiment has been carried out, where distributed O-RAN and mobile CN have been created to reflect the disaster use case.

A. Use Case Definition

The disaster scenario poses significant challenges for communication networks, as natural or man-made events can cause partial or complete loss of infrastructure. The 6G architecture presented addresses these challenges through its SBMA and closed-loop orchestration capabilities, enabling agile recovery by redeploying affected services across heterogeneous domains presenting resource availability while fulfilling requirements. The SBMA bus enables coordination across domains, and when combined with intent-based orchestration, allows the system to dynamically reorganize resources and services after a detected disruption. Each domain and each deployed service is equipped with the proposed connected tuples, which enable closed-loop AI-based control. These loops continuously monitor the state of the infrastructure and services running on it, detect failures, and trigger automated workflows to restore connectivity. In a disaster scenario, the architecture can (i) identify lost segments by obtaining telemetry and topology data from the connected tuples, (ii) decompose recovery intents into domain-specific actions (e.g., instantiate a new mobile CN instance, deploy RAN components, reconfigure transport paths), (iii) redeploy services on-demand using cloud-native principles, ensuring minimal downtime.

The ITU standardization body, in recommendation ITU-T L.392, focuses on shortening deployment time by optimizing the overall process and dividing deployment into phases, such as the *unit deployment phase* (which includes transportation and installation) and the *service set-up phase* [12]. In general, the timeframe for network recovery and deployment in disaster scenarios falls into two categories: (i) the *Seconds* requirement (Network Recovery/Recovery Time Objective (RTO)), which can be achieved through network redundancy; for example, traffic is automatically rerouted to a pre-built backup path when a primary path, such as a fiber line, fails; and (ii) the *Minutes-to-Hours* requirement (physical deployment), which refers to the need to establish new, temporary communications infrastructure within minutes to hours after a disaster, such as a hurricane or wildfire, has destroyed the original hardware. In this category, rapid deployment kits (such as Starlink kit, cell on wheels or cell on light truck [13]) can be set up and operational in as little as 15 to 30 minutes.

B. Achieved Results

To validate the feasibility of rapid recovery, we use results from a simplified testbed described in [14], where a cloud-native 5G network can be deployed on-demand, including RAN, Core, and Transport components. Briefly, the mobile network components can be distributed in three distributed PoPs interconnected with a ring transport network offering three differentiated transport paths. The experiments measured the time required to instantiate Mobile Core functions (control and user plane), Disaggregated RAN components (CU, DU), and Transport paths within an existing network topology. The different mobile network entities were packaged as independent NSs based on open source software (i.e., Open5GS and

(a) Deployment time of mobile core and disaggregated RAN entities.

(b) Deployment time of transport path in a ring topology of five nodes.

Fig. 4: Deployment times of mobile network entities and interconnection paths.

srsRAN project). Figure 4 presents a boxplot of deployment time for the different components:

- *Mobile instantiation* is completed in a mean time of 33 seconds for both control plane and 32 seconds for user plane (i.e., UPF NF).
- *RAN components* deployment times may vary depending on the number of DU/CU instances to recover, but remain in a mean time of 32 seconds per instance.
- For *Transport paths*, the reconfiguration of single independent transport flows considering three hops takes no more than 20 seconds per path, when done individually.

The results indicate that network entities can be instantiated in tens of seconds, with variations depending on component count and topology complexity. Consequently, end-to-end recovery after a disaster could be completed within minutes rather than hours, improving resilience compared to traditional manual solutions.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This article provided an in-depth review of the existing standardisation efforts towards the definition of an advanced service-based management architecture for the forthcoming 6G networks. In particular, the need for an intelligent cross-domain orchestrator was emphasized in light of its essential role of coordinating resources and data distribution across the 6G ecosystem, which thus emerges as a network of networks. The conducted analysis provided key insights into the overall architecture boundaries and the related building blocks in terms of DMO and IDM operating on top of the SBMA to achieve data continuum across the featured domains (i.e., RAN, transport, core, and AI/ML). The robustness and flexibility of the 6G architecture concept were eventually proven in the case of disaster management situations, confirming the added value in terms of short network restoration and deployment times that are essentially properties of next-generation 6G systems.

REFERENCES

[1] ETSI NFV, “Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV); Management and Orchestration; Report on Management and Orchestration,” ETSI

GR NFV-MAN 001 V1.2.1, European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), Dec 2021.

[2] Y. Wang, R. Forbes, U. Elzur, J. Strassner, A. Gamelas, H. Wang, S. Liu, L. Pesando, X. Yuan, and S. Cai, “From design to practice: ETSI ENI reference architecture and instantiation for network management and orchestration using artificial intelligence,” *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 38–45, 2020.

[3] L. Blanco, S. Via, C. J. Vaca-Rubio, E. Zeydan, L. M. C. Murillo, G. Kedar, G. R. Antonio, A. Antonopoulos, J. Haxhibeqiri, V. Maglogiannis, *et al.*, “UNITY-6G: UNified archITecture for Open RAN-enabled Distributed, Scalable and Sustainable Enhanced 6G Networks,” in *2025 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, pp. 440–445, IEEE, 2025.

[4] A. Mekrache, A. Ksentini, and C. Verikoukis, “Intent-based management of next-generation networks: an IIm-centric approach,” *IEEE Network*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 29–36, 2024.

[5] C. Benzaid and T. Taleb, “AI-driven zero touch network and service management in 5G and beyond: Challenges and research directions,” *Ieee Network*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 186–194, 2020.

[6] B. Chafika, T. Taleb, C.-T. Phan, C. Tselios, and G. Tsolis, “Distributed AI-based security for massive numbers of network slices in 5G & beyond mobile systems,” in *2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, pp. 401–406, IEEE, 2021.

[7] M. A. Uusitalo, P. Rugeland, M. R. Boldi, E. C. Strinati, P. Demestichas, M. Ericson, G. P. Fettweis, M. C. Filippou, A. Gati, M.-H. Hamon, *et al.*, “6G vision, value, use cases and technologies from European 6G flagship project Hexa-X,” *IEEE access*, vol. 9, pp. 160004–160020, 2021.

[8] 3GPP, “Management and orchestration; Architecture framework (Release 19),” tech. rep., 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), 2025.

[9] B. Barritt and W. Eddy, “Service management & orchestration of 5g and 6g non-terrestrial networks,” in *2022 IEEE Aerospace Conference (AERO)*, pp. 1–11, 2022.

[10] J. Baranda, M. Caus, L. Blanco, C. J. Vaca-Rubio, E. Zeydan, K. Dev, Z. Li, and T. De Cola, “On the architectural split and radio intelligence controller placement in integrated o-ran-enabled non-terrestrial networks,” *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 6, pp. 8571–8590, 2025.

[11] 3GPP, “Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Study on management and orchestration aspects of integrated satellite components in a 5G network,” 3GPP TR 28.808 V17.0.0, 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Mar 2021.

[12] ITU-T, “Disaster management for improving network resilience and recovery with movable and deployable information and communication technology (ict) resource units,” Recommendation L.392, April 2016.

[13] Aluma Tower Company, Inc., “What is a cell on wheels?,” Apr. 15 2025. Accessed: 11 August 2025.

[14] J. Baranda, J. V. Martínez, A. Bel, D. Gregoratti, L. M. Contreras, and J. Mangués-Bafalluy, “Full Orchestration of a Distributed 5G Cloud-Native Mobile Network: O-Ran, Core, and Transport,” in *2025 IEEE 11th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, pp. 315–317, 2025.